

interTwin

D4.4 First version of the DTs capabilities for High Energy Physics, Radio astronomy and Gravitational-wave Astrophysics

Status: APPROVED BY THE EC
Dissemination Level: public

Funded by the
European Union

Disclaimer: Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them

Abstract

Key Words

Digital Twin Engine, DT capabilities, High Energy Physics, GW Astrophysics, Radio Astronomy

This deliverable describes the release of Digital Twin (DT) applications that support the physics use cases and the implementation of the associated tools. It details the capabilities, characteristics, and describes the functional specifications of the DT applications and the status of their integration into the DTE architecture. Finally, it provides information about the next steps in the development and integration of those DTs.

Document Description			
First version of the DTs capabilities for High Energy Physics, Radio astronomy and Gravitational-wave Astrophysics			
Work Package number 4			
Document type	Deliverable		
Document status	APPROVED BY THE EC	Version	1
Dissemination Level	Public		
Copyright Status	<p>This material by Parties of the interTwin Consortium is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License.</p>		
Lead Partner	MPG		
Document link	https://documents.egi.eu/document/3940		
DOI	https://zenodo.org/records/14974752		
Author(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yurii Pidopryhora (MPG) • Kalliopi Tsolaki (CERN) • Sofia Vallecorsa (CERN) • Javad Komijani (ETHZ) • Marina Marinkovic (ETHZ) • Gaurav Sinha Ray (CSIC) • Isabel Campos (CSIC) • Lorenzo Asprea (INFN) • Francesco Sarandrea (INFN) • Sara Vallero (INFN) • Federica Legger (INFN) 		
Reviewers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Andrea Cristofori (EGI Foundation) • Dijana Vrbaneč (DESY) 		
Moderated by:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sjomara Specht (EGI Foundation) 		
Approved by	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Donatello Elia (CMCC) on behalf of TCB 		

Revision History			
Version	Date	Description	Contributors
V0.1	01/03/2024	ToC	Yurii Pidopryhora (MPG)
V0.2	13/05/2024	Version ready for internal review	All the authors
v0.3	21/05/2024	Version reviewed by internal reviewers	Andrea Cristofori (EGI Foundation) Dijana Vrbanec (DESY)
v0.4	28/05/2024	Version ready for TCB review	All the authors
v0.5	29/05/2024	Version reviewed by TCB	Donatello Elia (CMCC)
V1.0	30/05/2024	Final	

Terminology / Acronyms	
Term/Acronym	Definition
ML	Machine Learning
GAN	Generative Adversarial Networks
GW	Gravitational Wave
MCMC	Markov Chain Monte Carlo
QCD	Quantum Chromodynamics
QED	Quantum Electrodynamics
ILDG	International Lattice Data Grid
ILDG-MC	International Lattice Data Grid Metadata Catalogue
HEP	High Energy Physics
MC	Monte Carlo
HC-LHC	High Luminosity - Large Hadron Collider
DT	Digital Twin
CNN	Convolutional Neural Network
DTE	Digital Twin Engine
HPC	High Performance Compute
WP	Work Package
HPO	Hyper Parameter Optimization
HDF5	Hierarchical Data Format version 5
ONNX	Open Neural Network Exchange
ML-PPA	Machine Learning-based Pipeline for Pulsar Analysis
NF	Normalising Flow
TB	Terabyte
SQAaaS	Software Quality Assurance as a Service
PoC	Proof of Concept

Table of Contents

1	Introduction	8
1.1	Aim of this deliverable	8
1.2	Intended audience of this document	8
1.3	Structure of the document	8
2	DTs Application	9
2.1	DT Application: Lattice QCD simulation	9
2.2	DT Application: Detector simulation	10
2.3	DT Application: Noise simulation for radio astronomy	12
2.4	DT Application: VIRGO Noise detector	14
3	DTs Application First release	17
3.1	DT Application: Lattice QCD simulation	17
3.1.1	DTs Application Integrations	18
3.1.2	Scope and limitations	19
3.2	DT Application: Detector simulation	20
3.2.1	DTs Application Integrations	21
3.2.2	Scope and limitations	23
3.3	DT Application: Noise simulation for radio astronomy	24
3.3.1	DTs Application Integrations	24
3.3.2	Scope and limitations	25
3.4	DT Application: VIRGO Noise detector	27
3.4.1	DTs Application Integrations	28
3.4.2	Models and Data Requirements	29
3.4.3	Scope and limitations	29
4	Conclusions	31
5	References	32

Table of Figures

FIGURE 1 - DETAILED GRAPH REPRESENTATION OF THE TRAINING AND INFERENCE WORKFLOWS COMPOSITION (AS DESCRIBED ABOVE) OF THE FAST PARTICLE DETECTOR SIMULATION DT UTILISING 3DGAN APPROACH..... 11

FIGURE 2 - EXAMPLES OF FOUR MAIN TYPES OF DATA “TIME FRAMES” IN A PULSAR-OBSERVATION DATA SET, VISUALISED AS 256X256 IMAGES VERTICAL AXIS CORRESPONDS TO FREQUENCY, HORIZONTAL TO TIME, THE VALUE OF EACH POINT IS SIGNAL INTENSITY. THE TOP LEFT FRAME IS THE MOST COMMON ONE, “NONE” OR “EMPTY”, IT CONTAINS ONLY NOISE, AMPLIFIED DIFFERENTLY BECAUSE THE TELESCOPE’S SENSITIVITY IS DIFFERENT FOR DIFFERENT FREQUENCIES, LEADING TO APPARENT HORIZONTAL BANDING; THE TOP RIGHT AND BOTTOM LEFT FRAMES CONTAIN BROAD-BAND (BB) AND NARROW-BAND (NB) RADIO-FREQUENCY INTERFERENCE (RFI) REPRESENTED BY BRIGHTER VERTICAL OR HORIZONTAL STRIPES, THESE TYPES OF DATA ARE UNDESIRABLE BUT OFTEN RECORDED BECAUSE THE TELESCOPE IS SENSITIVE TO VARIOUS ARTIFICIAL OR NATURAL ELECTRO-MAGNETIC PHENOMENA (RADIO TRANSMISSIONS, EMISSIONS BY VARIOUS DEVICES, ELECTRIC STORMS ETC.). FINALLY, THE BOTTOM-RIGHT FRAME CONTAINS A PULSAR’S PULSE, REPRESENTED BY THE DIAGONAL SLIGHTLY CURVED LINE; THIS IS THE ONLY DESIRABLE TYPE OF DATA FRAME THAT WE WOULD LIKE TO SEPARATE FROM ALL THE OTHER TYPES. 14

FIGURE 3 - A SKETCH OF THE VETOING ALGORITHM. THE SAFE CONTROL CHANNELS ARE TAKEN AS INPUT BY THE GENERATIVE NN, WHICH THEN OUTPUTS THE GENERATED GLITCH. THE LOSS CHOSEN FOR THE TRAINING IS A SIMPLE L1 DISTANCE..... 15

FIGURE 4 - BLOCK DIAGRAM FOR THE METHOD OF NORMALIZING FLOWS. ξ AND ϕ ARE THE PRIOR AND TRANSFORMED FIELDS AT POSITION x . r AND q ARE THE CORRESPONDING PROBABILITY DENSITIES. THE GENERATE BLOCK ILLUSTRATES THE INTEGRATION OF NF AND MCMC BY INCLUDING AN ACCEPT/REJECT STEP. 18

FIGURE 5 - MIND MAP THAT ILLUSTRATES THE INTERCONNECTIONS BETWEEN THE LATTICE THEMATIC MODULES AND USE CASES WITH THE OTHER CORE SERVICES AND TOOLS WITHIN INTERTWIN AND WITH THE ILDG 2.0 INITIATIVE..... 19

FIGURE 6 - FAST PARTICLE DETECTOR SIMULATION DT USING ML TECHNIQUES HIGH LEVEL WORKFLOW COMPOSITION AND ITS CONNECTIONS WITH OTHER WORK PACKAGES’ COMPONENTS 21

FIGURE 7 - GENERAL OUTLINE OF THE DT STRUCTURE: MODELLING THE ASTROPHYSICAL SOURCE (PULSAR), TRANSMISSION OF THE SIGNAL THROUGH THE INTERSTELLAR MATTER, RECEIVING AND PROCESSING BY A RADIO TELESCOPE, ADDING SOURCES OF BOTH NATURAL AND ARTIFICIAL INTERFERENCE AND NOISE. 25

FIGURE 8 - LAYERED SOFTWARE ARCHITECTURE OF THE FRAMEWORK ML-PPA 26

FIGURE 9 - DIAGRAM OF THE FINAL SOFTWARE PRODUCT OF ML-PPA (IN THE C4 MODEL)..... 27

FIGURE 10 - SYSTEM CONTEXT DIAGRAM (IN THE C4 MODEL) OF THE DT FOR THE VETO PIPELINE..... 28

Executive summary

This document is deliverable 4.4 of the interTwin project, part of work package 4. It is a report collectively written by the partners of tasks 4.1, 4.2, 4.3 and 4.4, who are directly involved in designing digital twins for the physics domain (High Energy Physics, Radio Astronomy, and Gravitational Waves Astrophysics). The objective of this report is to provide an overview of the functionalities offered by each of the Digital Twins (DTs) and their current level of integration with the Digital Twin Engine (DTE).

It starts by outlining the capabilities of each DT application in general, demonstrating how they support their use cases and highlighting the specific features. Further description reviews the current release of each DT application, including the state of integration between each DT application and the main Core Components, as well as their integration with the Infrastructure Components. The next steps towards full integration are also discussed.

In general, every DT is uniquely crafted to target the particular task, offering new scientific tools that can be extremely helpful in the corresponding areas of physics.

1 Introduction

1.1 Aim of this deliverable

The overall objective of deliverable 4.4 is to provide information about the capabilities of DT Applications related to physical sciences (T4.1, T4.2, T4.3, T4.4). A Digital Twin application is a user-facing implementation of a DT. DT applications are the consumers of the capabilities offered by the interTwin DTE, thus introducing use case-specific requirements.

1.2 Intended audience of this document

The main audiences for the deliverable 4.4 are the **developers** and **end users**.

For the DT Application and DTE **developers**: this deliverable tells them about both planned and already implemented features of each of the DTs application, including interaction and integration with the underlying DTE modules. The DTE developers can then better understand the requirements of each use case, while for the DT Applications developers it serves as a reference. It gives insight to both categories on how the DTs will fit into the overall interTwin architecture by using specific Core Components.

For **end users**: the specified deliverable provides information on what are the capabilities of each specific DT in the physics domain. The users can find out what each DT is intended for, including the configurations, limitations, and possible customisations to meet the individual specific needs. By establishing a common framework for communication, stakeholders will be able to exchange information, validate models, and collaboratively address their challenges.

1.3 Structure of the document

The structure of this deliverable is as follows. [Section 2](#) gives an overview of each DT application. [Section 3](#) describes the status of each DT application at this stage of development. Finally, [Section 4](#) provides conclusions.

2 DTs Application

2.1 DT Application: Lattice QCD simulation

The purpose of Task 4.1 is to develop a Digital Twin (DT) application that can efficiently simulate quantum field theories on a lattice. It also seeks, in work jointly done with T7.1, to improve existing lattice DTs by integrating and tailoring services and tools being developed within interTwin into their existing workflows. The two parallel (and complementary) paths being explored involve:

- Developing Machine Learning based lattice simulations via the use of Normalising Flows (NF).
- Improving data management and software workflows for conventional lattice simulations.

As a statistical tool, Lattice QCD (LQCD) has been successfully used by physicists for decades to investigate and evaluate the Standard Model of Particle Physics. Importantly, it has been used to determine the quark masses and the strength of the Strong nuclear (QCD) interaction with steadily improving statistical precision (often in the wake of increased available compute capacity). However, despite LQCD's many successes the limitations of the current statistical algorithms lead to problems such as critical slowing down on lattices with physically interesting properties.

Machine learning algorithms provide an alternative approach to lattice simulations and early results suggest they could address some of the difficulties encountered with MCMC studies [R2]. We have been exploring deep generative models, in particular NF, in order to study alternatives to the standard algorithms used for generating lattice field configurations. We would like to be able to take a field theory and train a ML model up to a desired accuracy against that theory, before using the trained model to relatively cheaply generate the field configurations that constitute the basic research material of most lattice collaborations. The total cost in computing resources (primarily from training the model) should be comparable to or, ideally, cheaper than the total cost of field generation using the traditional MCMC methods. The application being developed is called **normflow**.

Large scale Lattice simulations take place in major HPC infrastructures at the national and international levels. From the infrastructure support point of view, increasing redundancy and enabling fast data transfer is vitally important, as many current competitive simulations today require the transfer of O (100)TB between HPC centres. At the moment a user is subject to the policies of their particular HPC centre(s). This makes sharing data between collaborators that do not both have classic ssh-based accounts on the same system difficult. Users would benefit from increased flexibility when accessing, uploading, and sharing scientific lattice data.

The **openQxD**¹ application is a good example of a current lattice application used for the competitive simulations referred to above. It is a program written in C for simulating QCD+QED field theories on 4D spacetime lattices. It lets the user configure, according to their research goals, a large number of physics and solver parameters, and is optimised to run at scale on large HPC systems. It takes as both input and output these large gauge field ensembles that have to be stored somewhere and should be easily accessible.

2.2 DT Application: Detector simulation

Task 4.2 concerns the design and development of a DT application for particle detector simulation. The requirements and functionalities of such a DT application have been described in detail in D4.2 [R1] and D7.2 [R3]. In the present deliverable section, the DT's goals and interface will be revised and updated.

Particle detectors measure different particle properties at colliders such as the Large Hadron Collider (LHC). More specifically, the detectors called calorimeters, responsible for measuring the energy of the particles, are key components of the whole experimental setup. In a collider, the emerging particles travel through the detector and interact with the detector material through the fundamental forces. In particular, within electromagnetic or hadronic calorimeters, showers of secondary particles are created due to the interaction of each new particle with the dense calorimeter material [R3]. The secondary particle creation process is inherently a complex stochastic process, and it is typically modelled using Monte Carlo (MC) techniques. These simulations have a crucial role in High Energy Physics (HEP) experiments, and at the same time are very resource-intensive from a computing perspective. Detector simulation allows scientists to design detectors and perform physics analyses.

The HEP community has long since started developing faster alternatives to Monte Carlo, including deep learning based techniques [R5, R6, R7]. In the calorimeter case, deep learning based fast simulation directly generates the detector output, without reproducing, step by step, each single particle that interacts with the detector material. More specifically, generative models have been used in related HEP applications, as they are able to combine deep learning with statistical inference and probabilistic modelling. A generative model's goal is to learn how to generate data based on a true, unknown distribution describing a finite number of observations.

The detector simulation DT accelerates particle detector simulations, leveraging generative AI methods. Our methodology is leveraging Geant4², a software toolkit for the simulation of the passage of particles through matter, to produce detector output data that then a Generative Adversarial Network (GAN), a class of machine learning frameworks for approaching generative AI, can be trained on. The technical requirements of such a DT have been identified, defined, and reported in detail in D7.2.

¹ <https://gitlab.com/rcstar/openQxD>

² <https://geant4.web.cern.ch/>

D4.4 First version of the DTs capabilities for High Energy Physics, Radio astronomy and Gravitational-wave Astrophysics

Compared to other generative approaches, the GAN approach is able to demonstrate highly realistic and sharp images [R8]. A GAN can learn a distribution implicitly as it does not rely on the explicit computation of probability densities. This use case utilises a 3D convolutional GAN (3DGAN), as calorimeter detectors can be regarded as huge cameras taking pictures of particle interactions [R9]. The voxels (3D calorimeter cells) are generated as monochromatic pixelated images with the pixel intensities representing the cell energy depositions.

Figure 1 - Detailed graph representation of the training and inference workflows composition (as described above) of the fast particle detector simulation DT utilising 3DGAN approach

A brief overview on the designed capabilities of the detector simulation DT is following. The DT operator is leveraging the Geant4 framework to produce data representing particles passing through a specific detector setup by employing MC-based simulations. The completion of this task is marked by the system's ability to successfully simulate particle passage through the specified detector setup and subsequently generate and store the simulation data for future use. Then, the data scientist's role involves preprocessing the simulated data to make it suitable for training the 3DGAN model in this case. This process is crucial to ensure that the data can effectively train the model. The requirement is met when the data scientist has access to the raw simulation data, and the system supports all necessary preprocessing and preparation steps, making the pre-processed data ready for model training. Subsequently, the DT user is responsible for training the GAN model on the pre-processed simulated data. Specific conditions such as the particle's entrance angle, initial energy, and type needs to be considered. The aim is to create a model that can reproduce data similar to the original simulated data. The process is considered successful if it can effectively use the pre-processed data, with the DT providing adequate tools for monitoring and tuning the training process, and the

system validating the trained GAN model through performance metrics. Finally, the user can leverage the trained GAN model during inference steps to facilitate fast GAN-based simulation. The objective is to produce simulation data faster compared to traditional Geant4 simulations. Success in this area is defined by the system's capability to generate accurate GAN-based simulation data under specific initial conditions, and its comparison for consistency and speed against traditional data. A more comprehensive and detailed description of the aforementioned DT processes can be found in the deliverable D4.2 [R1] and seen in **Figure 1**.

2.3 DT Application: Noise simulation for radio astronomy

Within Task 4.3 a DT of an astronomical source-telescope system is developed, able to generate synthetic output signals identical to the data recorded by a real telescope, including both scientifically valuable data and various interference and noise signals. Together with task 7.2, its goal is the creation of a larger framework called ML-PPA (for Machine Learning-based Pipeline for Pulsar Analysis) with a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN)-based ML classifier of the pulsar data, which can be trained using the DT-supplied data. The requirements and functionalities for these applications have been already described in D4.2 [R1] and D7.2 [R3]. A 50-page document [R10] has also been prepared by our team, giving a detailed overview and background of the project. Here we only provide a brief overview and update.

The main motivation for this work comes from the need to solve the problem of data overflow, which is about to become one of the largest issues in modern observational astronomy in general and radio astronomy in particular. The traditional paradigm of data reduction is not sufficient anymore and with the new generation of telescopes generating larger amounts of data, storing everything long term to allow inspection and analysis by human experts is no longer feasible. The so-called Square Kilometre Array (SKA)³ "pathfinders", such as South African MeerKAT⁴ or Australian ASKAP⁵ can produce several petabytes of raw data per week, thus it strains the capacity of even the best scientific facilities to keep their data sets even for weeks. When the SKA itself will be operational in a few years, the data flood will increase even further.

One way to deal with this is an ML-based data classification pipeline, able to both sort-out all of the scientifically not significant data in real time and alert human operators immediately when something relevant is found. The ML-PPA developed within tasks 4.3 and 7.2 is a pilot for just such a system.

An additional advantage of utilising an automated expert system like this is that it can react to unique events quickly enough for the new observational resources to be tasked with thoroughly studying them. This would allow it to systematically probe the transient

³ SKAO: <https://www.skao.int/en>

⁴ MeerKAT Radio Telescope: <https://www.sarao.ac.za/gallery/meerkat/>

⁵ ASKAP-radio telescope: <https://www.csiro.au/en/about/facilities-collections/atnf/askap-radio-telescope>

radio sky, which currently is generally unknown. Transients, meaning spikes of radiation that appear unpredictably in random directions, may result from very far and enormously energetic exotic events (like black hole collisions) and thus are invaluable sources of information in the areas of physics that cannot be studied experimentally in any other way, e.g. quantum gravity. If a signature of a transient source is encountered in the data flow, the automated expert system can trigger the “target of opportunity” alert for the detected anomaly, and notify the scientists on duty, who would decide then on the best course for further action. In turn, this may lead to a concerted effort of observing the target by a number of instruments, e.g. combining Earth-based radio observations with space-based optical and X-ray ones. An incredibly rare event, which would otherwise be only noticed later while reviewing the data record, can therefore be studied in much more detail and with all the available tools.

To be able to detect special and important events in the data, one first has to understand the regular and common features of the data stream well. In radio astronomy this primarily means noise and radio-frequency interference (RFI). Thus, a very important aspect of this project is understanding and modelling noise and RFI patterns in radio-astronomical data.

High data rates also require application of HPC in processing, however current common radio astronomy software is not well suited to this as it handles parallelization poorly. Another goal of this project is to create a well-scalable pipeline and test it with supercomputers.

Pulsars are ideal test subjects for this task, since they reliably produce periodic bursts of scientifically significant data with certain variability in signal strength and other parameters. Our first test data set is about 20 minutes of data collected by the Effelsberg 100m radio telescope⁶ observing one of the brightest and well-studied pulsars, the Crab pulsar. The size of the dataset is ~12.2 GB. The set is broken into more than 50,000 time frames, each with 256 spectra in it (**Figure 2**). These frames were looked through and labelled by hand, so the labelled set can be used for ML training or quality assessment. In the future we will use much longer data sets (up to 100 TB), of different sources and produced by other telescopes. In particular we have already negotiated to get data from one of the SKA pathfinders, MeerKAT, which will be the final testbed for this task and, as we hope, will ultimately use our software or its descendants in its actual day-to-day operation.

The ML data classification tool assigns labels to each data fragment, i.e. a time frame, based on the type of signal detected or not detected in it. The label describes the fragment on a basic level as “scientifically important data”, “no signal”, “interference of such and such type” etc., and in the future may also include more detailed properties. Since the proportions of each data type in the real data flow are very different (e.g. scientifically important data might constitute much less than 1% of the data sample), efficient ML training requires synthetic data to be used. That is where the DT comes in, a physical model of the source, its signal transmission and registration. Both the DT and

⁶ Radio Telescope Effelsberg: <https://www.mpifr-bonn.mpg.de/en/effelsberg>

D4.4 First version of the DTs capabilities for High Energy Physics, Radio astronomy and Gravitational-wave Astrophysics

ML-classifier are first written in Python, trying different approaches, but ultimately implemented in C++, ensuring high computational speed and scalability.

Figure 2 - Examples of four main types of data “time frames” in a pulsar-observation data set, visualised as 256x256 images. Vertical axis corresponds to frequency, horizontal to time, the value of each point is signal intensity. The top left frame is the most common one, “none” or “empty”, it contains only noise, amplified differently because the telescope’s sensitivity is different for different frequencies, leading to apparent horizontal banding; the top right and bottom left frames contain broad-band (BB) and narrow-band (NB) radio-frequency interference (RFI) represented by brighter vertical or horizontal stripes, these types of data are undesirable but often recorded because the telescope is sensitive to various artificial or natural electro-magnetic phenomena (radio transmissions, emissions by various devices, electric storms etc.). Finally, the bottom-right frame contains a pulsar’s pulse, represented by the diagonal slightly curved line; this is the only desirable type of data frame that we would like to separate from all the other types.

2.4 DT Application: VIRGO Noise detector

The purpose of Task 4.4 is to develop a Digital Twin (DT) application that can simulate glitches in the observational channel of the Virgo Gravitational Wave (GW) interferometer⁷ from its control channels.

A glitch is a transient noise artefact observed in the observational, *strain*, channel. Glitches can occur due to environmental reasons, such as seismic activity, or as a result of resonances in the detector’s subsystems. The monitoring of such effects is entrusted

⁷ <https://www.virgo-gw.eu/>

to a high number of control sensors, whose continuous data output is mapped onto so-called *auxiliary channels*. Glitches are divided into the classes identified by the GravitySpy project [R15].

The high number of observed glitches in the past observational runs and in the current O4b⁸ run makes it necessary to put into place effective vetoing procedures (Figure 3) for the identification and removal of bad data from the analyses' pipelines. For this reason, the project aims at identifying which auxiliary channels correlate strongly with the glitches observed in the strain and use generative methods to map the glitch from the former to the latter.

Figure 3 - A sketch of the vetoing algorithm. The safe control channels are taken as input by the generative NN, which then outputs the generated glitch. The loss chosen for the training is a simple L1 distance

The current implementation of the DT, as an intermediate release, consists of a train and inference subsystems implemented as a collection of Jupyter notebooks and installable Python packages via pip.

The primary aim of this release is to introduce the two packages **ANNALISA**, an installable Python package, and **GlitchFlow**, presently in the form of a Jupyter notebook. They are the main components of the training subsystem of the DT. The packages are used respectively for identifying the relevant auxiliary channels which the Neural Network (NN) will use as input and for the generation of glitches in the strain channel starting from the input data.

The inference subsystem is instead organised in two different Jupyter notebooks (Preprocess_API and Generative_API) respectively used for data preprocessing and dataset creation, and glitch generation. Preprocess_API is also used in the training subsystem.

ANNALISA (“Advanced Nonlinear transient-Noise Analyser of Laser Interferometer Sensor Arrays”) is a tool that makes use of time-frequency domain analysis of the data, namely the q-transform, to evaluate correlations among the main and auxiliary channels as the ratio of temporally coincident spikes in the energetic content of the signals above a critical threshold over the total number of spikes in the main channel.

⁸ <https://www.virgo-gw.eu/news/ligo-and-virgo-detectors-restart-gravitational-wave-observation/>

GlitchFlow is the module which contains the Generative Neural Network (GNN) for generating the glitches. In this first implementation of GlitchFlow, we rely on a ResNet12 architecture, due to it being simple and fast to train.

GNNs, and generative models more generally, are a class of machine learning algorithms designed to learn and mimic the underlying data distribution of a given dataset. The main idea behind generative models is to generate new data points that are similar to those in the original dataset. These models learn the complex patterns and structures present in the data, allowing them to generate novel samples that are indistinguishable from real data.

The training process involves feeding the generative model in GlitchFlow with data from the auxiliary channels identified by ANNALISA and the corresponding glitches observed in the main channel. Through iterative training, the model learns to capture the complex relationships and dynamics present in the data, allowing it to generate realistic glitches that accurately reflect the characteristics of the observed glitches.

Since the aim of the project is to implement a vetoing protocol to flag portions of the datastream as corrupted, it is of paramount importance to avoid the erroneous characterisation of GWs as glitches. The only way to achieve this is to provide as input to the NN only channels which do not detect any astrophysical signals; these channels are termed *safe channels*. A list of safe channels is available within the Virgo collaboration. This classification is constantly being updated for each new observational run, as channels are replaced, or their technical specifications are changed.

With tens of thousands safe channels in Virgo, feeding all of them into our analysis tool would be unfeasible. Instead, we leverage our understanding of specific glitch phenomena, such as scattered light glitches, which are currently the most frequent type observed. These glitches occur due to microseismic activity coupling with the detector, leading to photon scattering on moving reflective surfaces. By considering the physical origins of these glitches and their detection by sensors monitoring optical bench movement, velocity, or acceleration, we can identify relevant input channels possessing the expected units of these quantities. We also consider channels monitoring the global status of the interferometer's optical components. This approach ensures a more precise and effective channel selection process and allows us to restrict the correlation scan to a few hundreds of auxiliary channels.

The channels selected by the ANNALISA module, i.e. those showing a correlation coefficient above a tenable threshold, are then passed to Preprocess_API in order to create the dataset to train the GNNs in GlitchFlow for the task of glitch generation.

Once trained the model is then manually loaded as the generator in Generative_API.

3 DTs Application First release

3.1 DT Application: Lattice QCD simulation

Normflow is written in Python and uses the PyTorch library as its ML framework, with PyTorch functions modified and extended where required. For lattices of reasonable size, the training must be done on HPCs, either on CPUs or GPUs. The design of such a DT was described in Deliverable 4.2, section 3.1.2 [R1]. A technical specification about the resulting thematic module, **normflow**⁹, is given in D7.4, section 3.2 [R4].

Normflow is ultimately a proof of concept of a physics DT. It contains functions for the implementation of the method of NF as a generative model for lattice field theories. The workflow is straightforward, the user simply:

- Chooses a field theory,
- selects the desired model and training parameters,
- trains the model on many CPUs or GPUs, or on their own computer if the model is small enough.

The main idea behind NF methods is to build and train a neural network that maps a theory of interest to one that is easier to simulate, ideally to a theory in which the degrees of freedom are decoupled. Complex probability distributions can be accurately modelled by transforming samples from a simple distribution via a series of invertible transformations. Once such a map is found, one can then efficiently draw many samples from the theory of interest. We have been working with a method that combines a NF method with aspects of the MCMC method in order to improve efficiency and reduce autocorrelations. The basic algorithmic structure we are employing is shown in **Figure 4**.

Normflow currently supports the modelling of scalar theories in any number of dimensions. We are extending the package to include gauge theories with the goal of the efficient modelling of SU(2) and SU(3) gauge theories in 4D spacetime. In order to achieve this, one should ideally use a network that respects the gauge symmetry. As reported previously we are investigating networks that encode the necessary gauge-equivariant transformations. In addition, normflow now supports the saving and loading of models, this improves the robustness and flexibility of the training procedure and lets the end user debug the model at an intermediate stage if they wish so.

⁹ <https://github.com/jkomijani/normflow>

Figure 4 - Block diagram for the method of normalizing flows. ξ and ϕ are the prior and transformed fields at position x . r and q are the corresponding probability densities. The GENERATE block illustrates the integration of NF and MCMC by including an accept/reject step.

3.1.1 DTs Application Integrations

Figure 5 summarises the structure of the Lattice QCD project within interTwin and the extent of its integration with the other WPs.

Improvements to the software development workflow have been made by the integration of the Software Quality Assurance as a Service (SQAaaS) service being developed by WP6 - T6.2. Software quality assurance in this context involves making sure releases are tagged properly, documented well, and adhere to reasonable code style standards. SQAaaS has been integrated successfully into the normflow development workflow via GitHub Actions. Work is ongoing on integrating SQAaaS into a workflow involving openQxD, the established lattice code maintained by the RC* collaboration¹⁰.

In D7.2 we argued that lattice data could be more efficiently handled by adopting a data sharing model, and that this would be enabled by the data lake architecture proposed by interTwin's WP5 - T5.2. A testbed built along those lines is currently being operated by T5.2 from DESY, and sample lattice data was provided to them by us as part of the initial testing process. We were granted access to the testbed and have been able to test and familiarise ourselves with the Rucio protocol and its basic data management functionalities. As the testbed continues to expand and evolve we expect to move more data onto it and to more fully explore its robustness and advanced functionality. An overarching purpose of this federated data management project is the integration, at a fundamental level, of the FAIR principles into our data storage and retention policies.

Lattice collaborations have specific data management requirements that contrast with some of the other use cases. These include the existence of embargoed data, and fine-grained read/write permissions that would allow senior members to have more control over what other members are allowed to do with respect to specific data. Therefore, the WP5 group is working towards the creation of a tailored Virtual Organisation (VO) on a

¹⁰ <https://wordpress.ifca.es/rcstar>

separate data lake. Only members of the lattice VO will be able to authenticate into that data lake. A member of the lattice community will be trained as a Rucio administrator in order to manage this lattice data lake.

T5.2 has been working with the ILDG¹¹ developers and Rucio¹² engineers to integrate the ILDG Metadata Catalogue (ILDG-MC) with the data lake. We envision a Rucio instance, which is our entry point to the data lake, being able to associate an ILDG-MC entry with lattice data it can access. The ILDG-MC would list the location, as a Rucio address, of the data on the data lake, and the data would also list a reference for the entry in the ILDG-MC. If a researcher wanted to find a lattice ensemble with specific properties they could go to the ILDG-MC, search for it, and then would be directed to its location in the data lake. Although its feasibility is unclear at this stage another idea is that if lattice data is uploaded to the data lake an entry could be automatically written to the ILDG-MC.

The itwinai platform, under development by T6.5, is a framework for advanced ML workflows that is intended for use by DTs. We are working towards the creation of an operational normflow-itwinai use case that will be hosted on the official itwinai GitHub repository. As an alternative method of deployment, it could prove useful as a platform to more easily carry out hyperparameter optimisation.

Figure 5 - Mind map that illustrates the interconnections between the Lattice thematic modules and use cases with the other core services and tools within interTwin and with the ILDG 2.0 initiative.

3.1.2 Scope and limitations

The normflow application's scope extends as far as the simulation of QCD theories on reasonably sized lattices and the comparison of its performance with conventional lattice methods. It is hoped this work will guide the research community as to whether it is desirable, and if so in what manner, to integrate NF into their MCMC algorithms. While our results and the current results in the literature are promising and provide ample

¹¹ <https://hpc.desy.de/ildg/>

¹² <https://rucio.cern.ch/>

reason for continued research, it is at present unknown whether ML-based Lattice gauge field theory simulations that approach the physical point will be more efficient than MCMC simulations. There are also limitations imposed by using a ML-based method. A whole new set of models need to be developed for gauge theories, which are based on a particular class of complex matrices that collectively respect a huge class of the so-called gauge symmetries. Training these models, which typically require hyperparameter optimization, is a significant time and resource commitment.

3.2 DT Application: Detector simulation

This section provides an overview of CERN's digital twin application of a detector simulation, the current status of the DT and its integration with other DTE components (**Figure 6**). It describes the key steps, from particle simulations to event generation, and subsequent data comparison with real data. The process is explained in detail, highlighting the functionalities at each stage. Furthermore, it illustrates the flexibility in tuning the system to accurately represent various detectors' responses. This explanation is designed to give readers an understanding of the entire workflow design, shedding light on current practices and potential areas of future improvement. It also opens the way for a deeper discussion on the challenges faced, decisions made, and future strategies in the ongoing development of this innovative simulation application.

The detector simulation DT is described by two main workflows, the training workflow and the inference workflow, as seen also in **Figure 1**. The training workflow design includes the following functionalities, which run on HPC systems managed by Kubeflow containerized components. Geant4 simulates particle interactions, producing data based on a detector-specific configuration. The produced data consists of the energy measured by the detector sensors, the properties of the initial particle, such as its type, energy, and its trajectory angle with respect to the detector volume, and other metadata. The produced data, in ROOT format¹³, is stored at different data centres, with CERN currently serving as the primary storage site. The data produced from the traditional Geant4 simulation in ROOT format requires conversion into the HDF5¹⁴ format for further preprocessing before being input into the GAN model. The converted data will then be stored at data centres. Following the ROOT to HDF5 format conversion, the HDF5 data is further pre-processed and transformed into numpy arrays, a process currently incorporated within the model training scripts. The 3DGAN model is trained on the pre-processed data, conditioned on specific input describing the properties of the particles. The data is retrieved from the storage space where they reside. Hyperparameter optimization (HPO) will be employed to improve model performance. During validation and HPO, the model generated data and the Geant4 simulated data distributions will both be visualised. Additional validation techniques are currently being developed and established. At the end, the training workflow stores the optimised models, selected based on validation results.

¹³ <https://root.cern/>

¹⁴ <https://www.hdfgroup.org/solutions/hdf5/>

The inference workflow design includes the following functionalities. The 3DGAN model performs inference on specified initial conditions of a particle's energy and angle. After careful considerations and feasibility studies, this functionality currently will not be incorporated within the Geant4 application as reported during the designing phase of the DT. The GAN model completes the process of generating events, simulating the passage of particles through the calorimeter of a detector. Data distribution comparisons are drawn between the GAN-generated data and real data. These comparisons are essential for validating the efficacy and accuracy of the GAN-generated data.

Finally, based on the results visualised, two possible workflows are proposed for simulation tuning, shown in **Figure 1**. The model can either be re-inferred with different model input parameter values, provided these parameter values have been accounted for during model training. Alternatively, if a different value range of the conditional parameters is needed, the training workflow must be re-run from the beginning and new simulated data would need to be produced using the Geant4 application. These two possible workflows allow for greater flexibility and adaptability in tuning the detector's responses to various particle interactions.

3.2.1 DTs Application Integrations

The workflows of the particle detector simulation DT (**Figure 6**) described above will exploit the several components from the project's DTE and the related activities towards integration with these components have been performed.

Figure 6 - Fast particle detector simulation DT using ML techniques high level workflow composition and its connections with other work packages' components

The workflows depend on the WP7 3DGAN component¹⁵ reported in D7.4 [R4]. 3DGAN is a deep learning model for generation of images of calorimeter energy depositions. In preparation for the integration of the detector simulation DT with the first version of the AI workflow toolkit, we have developed a 3DGAN version based on the PyTorch Lightning ML framework. 3DGAN is being trained to produce images similar to the ones that are produced by Monte Carlo simulations. As the calorimeter detectors consist of layers of cells, those cells are modelled as monochromatic pixelated images with the cell energy depositions being the pixel intensities. 3DGAN consists of 2 networks, a generator and a discriminator, the two networks compete with each other trying to optimise a loss function until the convergence point, where the discriminator won't be able to distinguish the images generated by the generator from the real images. Each network is being trained using 3-dimensional convolution layers to represent the 3 spatial dimensions of the calorimeter images.

The current status of the particle detector simulation DT includes activities towards the implementation of the validation framework of the model's performance. This involves analysis Python scripts that compare the GAN generated images to Geant4 data events. All of the scripts take a sample of Geant4 events and then generate GAN events with similar input conditions, particle energy and particle angle. In the following months this work will be published in the related use case GitHub repository.

Integration activities of the SQAaaS service¹⁶ being developed by T6.2 have been performed. Software quality assurance in this context involves making sure releases are tagged properly, documented well, and adhere to reasonable code style standards. SQAaaS has been integrated successfully into the detector simulation ML development workflow via GitHub Actions. During the remainder of the project, improvements to the software development workflow will be made in the framework of integration of the SQAaaS service also with the model validation codebase.

The integration with itwinai framework has been successfully completed. The work can be found under this Github branch:

https://github.com/interTwin-eu/itwinai/tree/3dgan_integration

Itwinai developed under T6.5 is a Python library that streamlines AI workflows, while reducing coding complexity. It seamlessly integrates with HPC resources, making workflows highly scalable and promoting code reuse. With built-in tools for hyper-parameter optimization, distributed machine learning, and pre-trained ML models, itwinai empowers AI researchers. It also integrates smoothly with Jupyter-like GUIs, enhancing accessibility and usability. With itwinai exploitation we have managed to represent our AI workflows in a modular and reproducible way using configuration files, which break down the training and inference workflows into steps. The steps included are data loading, pre-processing, ML training and testing. In that way, there is a unified entry point from which the whole AI workflow can be configured and modified in successive executions. Through using itwinai for training 3DGAN, we can easily inspect

15

<https://github.com/interTwin-eu/DetectorSim-3DGAN/tree/main>

¹⁶ <https://confluence.egi.eu/display/interTwin/Use+cases+tracking>

and analyse the results from MLFlow¹⁷ dashboards, as well as store and manage models in the provided model registry.

Moreover, T5.2 engineers have successfully uploaded the simulated data produced by Geant4 and transformed into HDF5 format, into the interTwin data lake¹⁸.

Through the integration of the particle detector simulation DT with itwinai framework, the DT has been successfully deployed accessing the project infrastructure resources. Exploiting a TOSCA template and a deployed Kubeflow instance (T6.4), developers have managed to access Jupyter notebooks and deployed the detector simulation use case. The configuration files described above were used again and were translated into relevant Kubeflow pipelines¹⁹.

Furthermore, the detector simulation use case has been deployed through itwinai package inside a Docker container using interLink²⁰. The training was executed at the Jülich Supercomputing Centre exploiting interLink. By defining a Kubernetes pod, developers managed to allocate desired hardware (GPUs) for the model training process. The training was then executed by using an itwinai use case image that was staged beforehand and by stating the training command as defined in the itwinai configuration files mentioned above.

Finally, since the training of the 3DGAN model is completed in HPC and cloud resources, developers have used the model in inference mode to make predictions and produce detector output. This was achieved by exploiting OSCAR²¹. OSCAR is a serverless computing platform that is accessing HPC resources and offloading computations using interLink for federated computing infrastructure. Through an itwinai inference pipeline of the 3DGAN detector simulation and exploiting the use case image plus the shell script to be executed that performs the inference from the input data, the data flow created could be inspected and the storage events were monitored. Data produced during inference were uploaded to dCache, which activates an OSCAR service to process this data, by offloading a job to the specified computing resources. In that matter, the particle detector simulation DT was successfully integrated with the aforementioned DTE components and offloaded for inference to a VEGA node. All the above processes can also be watched at the first interTwin engine demo²², where the detector simulation use case is being used for testing and experimentation.

3.2.2 Scope and limitations

By developing the particle detector simulation use case and integrating it with the DTE components, we aim to provide a seamless Proof of Concept (PoC) of a physics DT leveraging ML capabilities.

¹⁷ <https://mlflow.org/>

¹⁸ <https://confluence.egi.eu/display/interTwin/Data+Samples+from+the+Use+Cases>

¹⁹ <https://www.kubeflow.org/docs/components/pipelines/v1/introduction/>

²⁰ <https://github.com/interTwin-eu/interLink/tree/main>

²¹ https://docs.google.com/document/d/1AxD8kXddzSgePBc3X7381YP1T_EbDWwu3Xb38ox1a-k/edit

²² https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=NoVCfSxwtX0&ab_channel=interTwin

The scope includes the development and implementation of both training and inference workflows, using high-performance computing systems. These workflows involve the simulated data conversion and preprocessing, and the training of the 3DGAN model to generate calorimeter energy depositions that mimic real detector outputs. The DT leverages ML frameworks such as PyTorch Lightning and the itwinai package. This integration facilitates scalable and efficient training, model validation, and inference processes, thereby enhancing the overall effectiveness and accessibility of the AI workflows.

The DT in the continuity of the project will also employ hyperparameter optimization (HPO) to fine-tune the model performance and incorporate extensive validation techniques. This ensures that the 3DGAN-generated outputs are accurate representations of the Geant4 simulated data, which is crucial for reliable detector simulations. The workflows exploit various other components, such as the interTwin data lake, interLink, OSCAR and SQAaaS. These integrations help in managing the data effectively and maintaining high standards in software development and deployment.

The DT's efficacy depends on the 3DGAN model's ability to generalise from the trained scenarios. Changes in the detector configurations or operating conditions that were not included in the training data might require retraining of the model, which can be resource intensive. Continuous validation is critical to ensure the model's outputs remain reliable over time. There is also a risk of bias in the model outputs if not adequately addressed during the model training and validation phases, which could lead to inaccurate simulations. Moreover, the integration of multiple components and services introduces complexity. This could lead to challenges in maintaining system stability and troubleshooting, especially when deploying updates or new features.

By understanding these scope and limitations, the involved stakeholders can better manage their expectations and plan for future enhancements to ensure the DT remains a robust and valuable PoC for CERN's particle detector simulations.

3.3 DT Application: Noise simulation for radio astronomy

This DT application addresses the challenge of identifying radio signals from intermittent astrophysical sources from large-volume data streams during the data acquisition phase. One of the main tasks is to identify noise and interference signals coming from different sources. The DT recreates the propagation of pulsar signals from the source to radio astronomical antennas and then processing them by radio telescope electronics, aiming to generate synthetic output signals identical to the data recorded by real telescopes. It is a part of a larger framework ML-PPA. In addition to the DT, it includes a CNN-based ML classifier of the pulsar data, which can be trained using the DT-supplied data.

3.3.1 DTs Application Integrations

One of the datasets has been loaded into the Data Lake and access to it successfully tested in collaboration with the working group in T5.2, further and more sophisticated

tests are currently in the works. The ways of integrating with the Core Components are investigated in close collaboration with our DT developers and the DTE developers of the working group in WP6.

3.3.2 Scope and limitations

Currently, four software modules have been released (as described in D7.4, R4), all under the umbrella designation of ML-PPA:

- [PulsarDT](#)
- [PulsarRFI_Gen](#)
- [PulsarRFI_NN](#)
- [PulsarDT++](#)

PulsarDT: A physics-based DT that simulates the propagation of pulsar signals from the source to the antennas ([Figure 7](#)) and generates synthetic data. It is written in Python to test algorithmic strategies for physical models of pulsars, interstellar medium, telescopes, interference and noise, that will be later implemented in PulsarDT++.

Figure 7 - General outline of the DT structure: modelling the astrophysical source (pulsar), transmission of the signal through the interstellar matter, receiving and processing by a radio telescope, adding sources of both natural and artificial interference and noise.

PulsarRFI_Gen: An empirical DT that generates “timeframes”, 2D images (time-frequency) of all possible types of telescope output from a pulsar observation: pulses (scientifically relevant data), two different types (“narrow” and “broad”) of RFI signals, and “empty” frames, containing only noise. It creates these timeframes by mimicking available real data (based on the geometry of images, noise characteristics etc.) rather than generating them from the physical first principles as PulsarDT does. The purpose of this tool is to have enough training data for the ML classifier while the much more complicated physics-based DT is still being developed.

PulsarRFI_NN: The ML classifier, that is a CNN-based tool for identification of various types of pulsar and RFI signals. Just like PulsarDT, it is a Python-based testing ground for various algorithms that will later contribute to PulsarDT++.

PulsarDT++: This is a C++ implementation of PulsarDT and PulsarRFI_NN with a general test of architecture of the whole ML-PPA package (see [Figures 8](#) and [9](#)). The released version (0.1) includes:

D4.4 First version of the DTs capabilities for High Energy Physics, Radio astronomy and Gravitational-wave Astrophysics

- a layered architecture: a Python-based user interface on the top of a layer with various modules for time-critical analyses (using C++),
- a simplified simulation model of pulsar signals,
- real data (the Effelsberg - Crab pulsar dataset, as described in [Section 2.3](#)) and synthetic data (generated by PulsarRFI_Gen) of pulsar and RFI signals,
- a container with all necessary components.

Figure 8 - Layered software architecture of the framework ML-PPA

D4.4 First version of the DTs capabilities for High Energy Physics, Radio astronomy and Gravitational-wave Astrophysics

Figure 9 - Diagram of the final software product of ML-PPA (in the C4 model)

3.4 DT Application: VIRGO Noise detector

The core of the VIRGO Noise detector DT is a Generative Adversarial Network used to find the transfer function of the system producing non-linear noise in the detector output. The information produced by the GAN is used to identify the presence of transient noise (glitches) in incoming data, which could mimic a signal of astrophysical origin (the gravitational wave).

The GAN model should learn to simulate the signal in the strain channel starting from the signal in a subset of auxiliary channels, therefore reproducing the noise component of the strain signal only. By comparing the simulated strain signal with the real signal, one should be able to infer the presence of an astrophysical signal.

The DT is organised as a pipeline operating in quasi real-time (low-latency), with the goal of identifying a glitch in the incoming data and passing the information to downstream low-latency pipelines that search for transient astrophysical signals. In the first phase, the information will be passed as a veto decision not to process the data if they contain a glitch. In a second phase, also in view of the Einstein Telescope, the DT will output

denoised data, in which the glitch has been removed, to be further processed by the search pipelines.

3.4.1 DTs Application Integrations

All the modules described in [section 2.4](#) are set up in Docker containers, so that they can be deployed in different machines. The pipeline integration between the data lake and the containerised modules is being developed in collaboration with the working group in T5.2. The DT is being implemented as a set of interdependent Airflow²³ DAGs.

The high-level architecture of the DT has been defined in deliverable 7.2 section 2.3.1 [R3]. We show here the C4 model of the DT veto pipeline ([Figure 10](#)). This was also already presented in deliverable 7.2 and it is repeated here for clarity.

Figure 10 - System Context diagram (in the C4 model) of the DT for the veto pipeline.

²³ <https://airflow.apache.org/>

3.4.2 Models and Data Requirements

Both the Annalisa and GlitchFlow packages make use of the classes and functionalities implemented in the GWpy²⁴ package, which contains tools for the study of GWs signals.

The data used for the off-line analysis and benchmarking was downloaded from the central computing facility of the Italian Institute for Nuclear Physics (INFN).

A pip-installable version of the Annalisa package, the Jupyter notebook containing GlitchFlow, and the preprocessing module can all be found in a GitHub repository:

- **Annalisa:** https://github.com/interTwin-eu/DT-Virgo-notebooks/tree/main/WP_4_4/Annalisa-0.1.tar.gz
- **GlitchFlow:** https://github.com/interTwin-eu/DT-Virgo-notebooks/blob/main/WP_4_4/interTwin_wp_4.4_synthetic_data.ipynb
- **Preprocess_API:** https://github.com/interTwin-eu/DT-Virgo-notebooks/blob/main/WP_4_4/Preprocess_API.ipynb.

We detail the data that is used as input for both tools described in [section 2.4](#).

Annalisa

The input data consists of time series contained in the strain and the physically selected auxiliary channels, stored in files in HDF5 binary data format. The data is extracted from the files and read as GWpy TimeSeries objects.

The time series need to have a minimum length of six seconds and they must include a time in which a glitch was observed in the strain channel, so that a meaningful correlation analysis can be performed.

GlitchFlow

The input data consists of time series contained in the strain and the auxiliary channels which have been identified as highly correlated with it by Annalisa. The data is once again converted into GWpy TimeSeries objects, but the tool does not rely on any specific file format for data storage and access. The duration of the signals in the TimeSeries can be freely set by the user.

3.4.3 Scope and limitations

When the Annalisa and GlitchFlow are combined in an integrated workflow they allow the user to:

- identify how sensitive each auxiliary channel is to a specific glitch
- use the data of said auxiliary channels to reliably generate a glitch in the strain channel
- implement an off-line vetoing protocol for GW detector events

²⁴ <https://github.com/gwpy/gwpy>

D4.4 First version of the DTs capabilities for High Energy Physics, Radio astronomy and Gravitational-wave Astrophysics

Further work is under way to improve the denoising performance. Currently, the tools present the following limitations:

- vetoing and denoising analyses have only been performed on the scattered light glitches
- glitch subtraction from the strain channel cannot be performed for glitches of medium or low intensity

4 Conclusions

The first release of the interTwin DTs applications for WP4 focused on the physics domain was developed during the first 18 months of the project. In the current deliverable D4.4, the main focus is on specifying (in [Section 2](#)) the capabilities of each specific DT (T4.1, T4.2, T4.3, and T4.4) and describing the current release (in [Section 3](#)), its integration with the Data Lake provided by WP5 and the Core Components provided by WP6, along with schematic high-level workflows. The current scope and limitations of this first release are identified for each individual task.

The next step will be to complete the development and the integration of this first release of each DT Application. This deliverable is a first overview of the future prototypes of the DT applications for the physics domain in the DTE architecture.

5 References

Reference	
No	Description / Link
R1	interTwin D4.2 First Architecture design of the DTs capabilities for High Energy Physics, Radio astronomy and Gravitational-wave Astrophysics (EC approved). A. Manzi <i>et al.</i> (2023). DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10417138
R2	Flow-based generative models for Markov chain Monte Carlo in lattice field theory. M. S. Albergo, G. Kanwar, and P. E. Shanahan <i>Phys. Rev. D</i> 100, 034515 (2019) DOI: https://link.aps.org/doi/10.1103/PhysRevD.100.034515
R3	interTwin D7.2 Report on requirements and thematic modules definition for the physics domain (EC approved). K. Tsolaki <i>et al.</i> (2023). DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.8036996
R4	interTwin D7.4 First version of the thematic modules for the physics domain (Submitted to EC). G. S. Ray <i>et al.</i> (2023). DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10224277
R5	Fast Simulation for ATLAS: Atfast-II and ISF. W. Lukas. Technical Report ATL-SOFT-PROC-2012-065, CERN, Geneva, Jun (2012) DOI: https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/396/2/022031
R6	Fast simulation of the CMS detector. D. Orbaker. <i>J. Phys. Conf. Ser.</i> , (219):32–53, 2010. Part of Proceedings, 17th International Conference on Computing in High Energy and Nuclear Physics (CHEP 2009): Prague, Czech Republic (2009). DOI: https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/219/3/032053
R7	Fast simulation of electromagnetic showers in the ATLAS calorimeter: Frozen showers. E. Barberio <i>et al.</i> <i>J. Phys. Conf. Ser.</i> , 160, 012082, (2009). DOI: https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/160/1/012082
R8	Generative Adversarial Networks. Ian J. Goodfellow <i>et al.</i> DOI: https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1406.2661
R9	Fast Simulation of a High Granularity Calorimeter by Generative Adversarial Networks. Gul Rukh Khattak <i>et al.</i> https://arxiv.org/abs/2109.07388 DOI: https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2109.07388
R10	ML-based Pipeline for Pulsar Analysis (ML-PPA). Andrei Kazantsev, Tim Oelkers, Yurii Pidopryhora, Tanumoy Saha, Marcel Trattner, and Hermann Heßling (2023). DOI: https://gitlab.com/ml-ppa/gitlab-profile/-/blob/main/PUNCH_interTwin_project.pdf
R11	Zevin, Michael, et al. "Gravity Spy: integrating advanced LIGO detector characterization, machine learning, and citizen science. M. Zevin <i>et al.</i> DOI: https://arxiv.org/abs/1611.04596

